

The impact of realistic red supergiant mass-loss on stellar evolution

Emma R. Beasor

NSF's NOIRLab 950 N. Cherry Ave., Tucson, AZ 85719, USA

Mass-loss in stellar models

Directly linking massive stars to their explosive endpoints is a fundamental aim in stellar astronomy. Stars with initial masses (M_{ini}) between $8 - 30M_{\odot}$ are expected to evolve to become red supergiants (RSGs) before exploding as hydrogen-rich Type II-P supernovae (SNe). However, the apparent lack of Type II SN progenitors with initial masses above $\sim 17M_{\odot}$ [1] has led many studies to speculate on possible alternative fates for the more massive objects, including whether or not these stars undergo strong enough mass-loss that they peel away their own hydrogen envelope, causing them to die as stripped-stars and produce hydrogen-poor (or Type Ibc) SNe.

Stellar evolutionary models have demonstrated that mass-loss during the cool supergiant (CSG) phase ($T_{\text{eff}} < 10,000\text{K}$) can have a major effect on where on the Hertzsprung-Russel diagram (HRD) a star will end its life [2]. If a star has a strong enough wind it can self-strip its H-envelope and return to the blue side of the HRD, no longer producing a Type II SNe upon death. Instead, it will produce a stripped Type I SNe (e.g. Type Ib/c). This has been touted as a potential explanation

It is important to note that unlike hot star mass-loss, mass-loss rates (\dot{M}) during the CSGs, and in particular RSGs, phases are poorly understood and currently cannot be reliably determined from first principles. Instead, stellar models rely on purely empirical $\dot{M}-L_{\text{bol}}$ relationships. The most widely used of these prescriptions is that of de Jager et al. (1988, hereafter dJ88 [3]), a literature review in which the authors collated all available \dot{M} measurements in the literature for stars of spectral types O through M, though it is no longer used for hot stars. The prescription itself contains only a handful of RSGs (15), and has a high level of internal scatter (around a factor of 10, see e.g. [4]), likely due to the lack of constraints on initial mass and metallicity [5]. This high level of uncertainty could be the difference between a star losing all of its H-envelope, or none of it at all.

To better understand the pre-SN evolution of massive stars we re-appraised the mass-loss rates of RSGs in 4 young local group clusters of different ages (hence containing RSGs of different initial masses) using modern data sets. By doing this, we were able to observe how \dot{M} changes as a star evolves up the RSG branch, as well as how the $\dot{M}-L_{\text{bol}}$ relation changes as a function of initial mass. From this, we were able to derive an initial-mass dependent mass-loss rate prescription (hereafter B20) for use in stellar models [6]. An initial back of the envelope comparison demonstrated that compared to the \dot{M} implementation in the Geneva evolutionary models,

Input in evolutionary models

Using our new prescription we performed a comparative

study to the MESA-MIST stellar isochrones [7] which use the dJ88 prescription during the RSG phase. To directly compare the effects of using our updated prescription derived with cluster RSGs, we simply changed only the mass-loss rate implementation during these phases, swapping the dJ88 prescription for B20, while leaving all other parameters unchanged, and computed a new grid of stellar models with initial masses between $12 - 27M_{\odot}$.

While the final position on the Hertzsprung-Russel diagram did not change for these stars, there was a significant difference in the amount of H-envelope retained at core-collapse. In Figure 1 we show the H-rich envelope mass at CC as a function of the initial mass of the star, for both the standard MIST models and for the new models incorporating the B20 prescription. For the models using the dJ88 prescription the final H-envelope mass appears to plateau at $\sim 8M_{\odot}$, whereas for the models including the B20 prescription we see a positive correlation between H-rich envelope mass and initial mass. This means that in progenitor models, the majority of which use the dJ88 prescription, the parameter of H-envelope mass has effectively been held as a constant.

Figure 1: H-envelope mass at core-collapse as a function of initial mass, where the blue triangles represent models using standard dJ88 \dot{M} and the pink squares represent models using the B20 prescription.

Could an extreme mass-loss phase affect evolution?

Quiescent mass-loss throughout the RSG phase has been shown to be significantly lower than previous prescriptions have suggested. Implementing a new prescription in evolutionary models has shown that quiescent winds are incapable of removing a significant fraction of H-envelope, and as such stars in the $20-40M_{\odot}$ range would be unable to form stripped type stars via single star evolution. However, it has been suggested that dust-enshrouded RSGs (DE-RSGs) may represent a short-

lived, high mass-loss phase with the ability to peel away a large fraction of H-envelope in a short space of time. Indeed, some models do adopt enhanced mass-loss for at least a fraction of the RSG phase (e.g. Geneva), motivated by the van Loon et al. 2005 prescription (hereafter vL05 [8]), which was derived from a sample of DE-RSGs identified in the Large Magellanic Cloud (LMC).

The vL05 sample were selected based on their large mid-IR excess and, in some cases, strong maser emission, both indicative of strong mass-loss. Despite their rarity ([9] find that above a luminosity of $\log L/L_{\odot} = 5.0$ only 9 out of 73 cool supergiants are DE-RSGs), the \dot{M} of the vL05 DE-RSG sample are claimed to be more than a factor of 10 higher than the quiescent mass-loss seen in the cluster RSGs [5, 6], which could potentially allow a significant fraction of H-envelope to be removed in a short amount of time.

However, the definition of a DE-RSG is somewhat subjective. Quiescent mass-loss throughout the RSG phase is only able to remove $\sim 1M_{\odot}$ of material. As such, we define the DE-RSG phase by quantifying how strong the mass-loss would need to be to remove a large enough fraction of H-envelope and force an RSG to evolve back to the blue of the HRD. To achieve this a star would need to be experiencing mass-loss rates of $1 \times 10^{-4}M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ for around 10% of the $\sim 10^6$ yr RSG phase. This would strip $10M_{\odot}$ of material, and allow the star to return to the blue of the HRD and die as a H-poor supernova. The high mass loss would result in high extinction ($A_V > 2$ mag) and a large infrared excess (see Figure 1 in [10]).

Using an updated photometric catalogue of RSGs in the LMC we take another look at the purported DE-RSGs, and find that in colour-magnitude space they *do not stand out as a unique group*, in conflict with the suggestion they represent a specific phase of evolution for all RSGs (see Figure 2). Instead, we find that only 1 object in the entire LMC, WOH G64, fits the necessary criteria to be classified as a bona-fide DE-RSG, having a high optical extinction (> 8 mag) and a high mass-loss rate ($> 10^{-4}M_{\odot} \text{ yr}^{-1}$).

If DE-RSGs *do* represent a short lived phase of massive star evolution it is extremely short lived (lasting less than 3% of the RSG lifetime), and likely only able to remove $\leq 2M_{\odot}$ of material. This is *not enough* to drive a

single star back to the blue of the HRD.

Overall, this means that low-luminosity Wolf-Rayet stars, blue supergiants, and luminous blue variables are unlikely to arise from post-RSG evolutionary phases in single stars. It also means that the relatively low initial mass progenitors of Type Ibc and Type IIb SNe ($M_{ZAMS} \leq 40M_{\odot}$) cannot form via a single-star pathway. Crucially, since above $40M_{\odot}$ most stars exist in binaries [11], we can effectively rule out the single star evolutionary pathway for the formation of stripped stars and supernovae entirely. Instead, we suggest that the ratio of stripped and unstripped SNe is driven by binarity.

Figure 2: Colour-magnitude diagram for cool supergiants in the LMC. Red circled objects represent the original DE-RSG sample. Taken from [10].

References

- [1] Smartt, S., 2009, MNRAS, 395, 1409
- [2] Georgy, C., 2012, A&A, 538, L8
- [3] de Jager, C., et al., 1988, A&AS, 72, 295
- [4] Maun & Josselin, 2011, A&A, 526, A156
- [5] Beasor, E., & Davies, B., 2018, MNRAS, 475, 55
- [6] Beasor, E., et al., 2020, MNRAS, 492, 5994
- [7] Choi, J., et al., 2016, ApJ, 823, 102
- [8] van Loon, J. Th., et al., 2005, A&A, 442, 597
- [9] Davies, B., et al. 2018, MNRAS, 478, 3138
- [10] Beasor, E., & Smith, N., 2022, ApJ, 933, 41
- [11] Sana, H., et al., 2012, Science, 337, 444

Short CV

2015: Master in Astrophysics, University of Liverpool, UK
 2015–2019: PhD in Astronomy, Liverpool John Moores University, UK
 2019–2022: NASA Hubble Fellow, NSF’s NOIRLab, USA
 2022–present: Bok Fellow, University of Arizona, USA